

A REAL-TIME EMBODIED SONIFICATION MODEL TO CONVEY TEMPORAL ASYMMETRY DURING RUNNING

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ABSTRACT

Existing research has shown that auditory biofeedback can be a powerful tool in improving athletic performance, exploiting the otherwise under-used auditory channel to convey relevant kinematic information. To date, however, no such research has focused on running gait asymmetry, which has a proven link to running economy (energy expenditure). In this work, we designed and developed an intuitive sonification scheme for conveying temporal asymmetry to a runner. It specifically conveys short- and medium-term information on ground contact time asymmetry and cadence through a set of embodied metaphors. We first developed and validated a lightweight algorithm for detecting running gait events, cadence, and ground contact time balance based on data from a single inertial sensor. These features were used as control parameters to a complex FM synthesis engine. The gait detection and sonification systems were implemented in a proof-of-concept application allowing real-time manipulation of system parameters to facilitate the user-centred design of a feasible and usable sonification topology. We hope that the application can form the basis for the development and evaluation of a wearable system for providing gait asymmetry biofeedback to runners in real time.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interactive sonification can confer motor learning benefits when applied as a tool for augmented auditory feedback during exercise and sports [1, 2, 3]. The use of sound as a feedback modality here is particularly attractive as it does not interfere with an athlete's vision or divert visual attention from stimuli essential for performance and safety [2]. As also reviewed in [2, 4], the potential of real-time sonification to aid motor performance has been explored and documented for a wide range of activities including rowing [5, 6], speed skating [7], and running [8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. Running is one of the most popular sporting activities, and recent years have seen the proliferation of running wearables that provide real-time feedback on physiological and biomechanical variables [13]. However, the applicability of these wearables would be helped by an interdisciplinary framework that considers running from both an injury prevention and performance perspective; scientific literature [13, 14] suggests that biomechanical variables are suitable for feedback purposes if (a) they are strongly linked to injuries or running economy, (b) can be measured accurately in various conditions, and (c) are modifiable.

Gait asymmetry refers to differences in bilateral behavior of the legs, which is said to arise from limb dominance, disease, leg length differences, and strength imbalances [15]. For running,

no clear link between asymmetry and increased risk of exercise-related injury has been found [16], however, recent research has revealed a link between step time asymmetry (bilateral differences in step duration) and running economy [17]. Indeed, although *ideal* running gait may be presumed to be characterised by perfect mechanical symmetry, in reality even healthy runners exhibit some degree of asymmetry [18]. Running with asymmetric step times increases the rate of metabolic energy expenditure in unimpaired individuals [17]. In particular, every 10% increase in ground contact time asymmetry has been shown to increase net metabolic power by 7.8% [17]. Running asymmetry is known to increase as fatigue develops [19].

We therefore argue based on the criteria outlined in [13, 14] that temporal asymmetry is a relevant variable for the provision of real-time feedback. Gait asymmetry, represented as left-right ground contact time balance, is reported to runners in real time by commercial wearable devices such as Garmin *Running Dynamics*¹. This information is represented numerically or graphically, however, requiring that the runner alternate their visual focus between the running task and the display. Moreover, this entails that the runner must hold a small screen such that they are able to see it, an act physically incompatible with the arm-swinging inherent to running. The auditory medium is a suitable means to mitigate these issues.

Researchers have developed and tested a variety of applications aimed at conveying various aspects of running through sound, ranging from spatiotemporal [9, 12] to kinematic [8, 10, 11] and kinetic [20, 21] parameters, but asymmetry has not been sonified in any of the studies reviewed here. In the majority of cases, movement capture was carried out using wearable *inertial measurement units (IMUs)* [8, 9, 21, 11, 12, 22] mounted either on the lumbar spine or the lower extremities. From primarily accelerometer data, several biomechanical quantities such as cadence (step rate) [9, 11, 8], trunk tilt [11], vertical displacement [8, 11], tibial shock [21], horizontal and vertical acceleration [22] have been computed and sonified. Although there is only limited, conflicting, or inconsistent evidence supporting the relationship between the majority of previously sonified variables and running injuries or economy [13], most studies report that their sonification schemes elicited measurable changes in running technique during preliminary evaluation protocols.

In terms of conveying these quantities through sound properties, several parameter mapping approaches have been tested. Eriksson et al. [8] provided warning sounds through a bouncing ball metaphor if excessive vertical displacement was detected.

¹<https://discover.garmin.com/performance-data/running/#running-dynamics>

Forsberg [11] simultaneously mapped vertical displacement, cadence, and trunk tilt to manipulations to user-selected music, respectively through pitch transposition, tempo, and filtering parameters. Lorenzoni et al. [9] mapped deviations from a target cadence to the intensity of a noise signal mixed with user-selected music, and Van Berghe et al. [21] applied a similar approach, albeit sonifying tibial shock instead of cadence. In [9, 21], the sonification was found to have a measurable impact on runner cadence and tibial shock respectively. Moens et al. [23] synchronized pre-recorded music to the runner’s cadence, a paradigm that has been shown to elevate runners’ physiological effort at a high level of perceived exertion [24].

It has been shown to be possible to measure running gait phases (foot contact/non-contact and step/stride durations) and quantify asymmetry based on measurements from a single inertial sensor [19, 25]. Although this is the very tool used for movement capture in the majority of extant sonification systems, it was interesting to note that none of them measured or sonified any aspect of spatiotemporal asymmetry. Although the scope for asymmetry modification by runners is unclear, we believe that the potential of providing real-time sonified feedback on temporal asymmetry during running is worthy of scientific investigation. In this work, we propose a novel scheme for the provision of auditory feedback on temporal asymmetry during running. We first developed a method for real-time foot-strike and toe-off event detection during running using a single inertial sensor. We evaluated its accuracy on a recorded dataset of normal and simulated impaired running patterns at different speeds by one runner on a treadmill. Next, we developed an interactive sonification scheme aimed at providing intuitive and perceptually salient asymmetry feedback based on embodied metaphors. The subsequent sections provide details of our design philosophy, technical implementation, and links to audiovisual demonstrations.

2. GAIT EVENT DETECTION

2.1. Running Data Collection

In order to develop a gait event detection algorithm and demonstrate our asymmetry sonification scheme, we recorded motion data corresponding to several running speeds and two running types (normal, asymmetric) for analysis. The participant, a 36 y/o male (185 cm, 75 kg), was an experienced amateur runner with no documented physical impairment or injury at the time of data capture.

Setup: Data capture was conducted using a treadmill in a gymnasium setting. A Delsys *Trigno* wireless biofeedback system² was used for motion sensing (using three Delsys IMU sensors) and data communication (wirelessly over Bluetooth to the Trigno base station). The base station was connected to an IBM laptop computer running Delsys *EMGworks Acquisition* software and Delsys *EMGworks Analysis* software³ for storage and CSV export. The IMU sensors were attached directly to the runner’s skin by way of Delsys adhesive film; one at the anterior trunk, level with the sternum, and one each at the left and right lateral shank, roughly 5 cm above the ankle. The IMUs recorded three-axis accelerometer and gyroscope data with a sampling period of 6.75×10^{-3} s (≈ 148 samples per second). In addition, video footage was recorded on an Apple iPhone 11 Pro at 60 fps and

a resolution of 2160×3840 pixels. The phone was placed roughly 1.2 m away from the runner, at calf-height at a roughly isometric angle behind and to the right of the runner.

Procedure: Six capture sessions were recorded in all — *normal* running at four speeds, and *simulated asymmetric* running at two speeds. For normal running, the chosen speeds were 7.5 km/h, 10 km/h, 12.5 km/h and 15 km/h, representing a range from a slow jog to a moderately fast endurance-running pace; for the simulated asymmetric running the speeds were 7.5 km/h and 10 km/h. For each capture session, the runner started the treadmill and ran for approximately thirty seconds, at which point IMU data capture was begun. Sixty seconds of steady-state running was recorded, following which the treadmill was stopped and the runner performed isolated foot-strikes for purposes of later synchronising the video footage and IMU data.

Figure 1: Representative plots of synchronised filtered vertical axis gyroscope data (top) and vertical axis accelerometer data (middle) recorded by a trunk-mounted IMU for natural gait running at 10 km/h, plus *jerk* (bottom) calculated as per equation (1). Toe-off (T-O) events identified in the accelerometer data as a local maximum following a region of sustained positive jerk. Foot-strike (F-S) events identified as occurring four samples prior to the onset of a high negative-jerk region. Left vs. right foot identified at the toe-off event by consulting the sign of the filtered gyroscope signal. Note that temporal thresholds for T-O/F-S and F-S/T-O intervals are used to prevent spurious event detections at jerk fluctuations such as present at 21.9 s, 22.25 s and 22.48 s.

²<https://www.delsys.com/downloads/USERSGUIDE/trigno/wireless-biofeedback-system.pdf>

³<https://delsys.com/emgworks/>

Running Type	Speed (km/h)	Steps Recorded	Mean Error (s)	95% CI (s)
Natural	7.5	146	-0.0084	[-0.0089, -0.0078]
Natural	10	160	-0.0015	[-0.0020, -0.0009]
Natural	12.5	180	0.0053	[0.0046, 0.0060]
Natural	15	192	0.0121	[0.0114, 0.0129]
Asymmetric	7.5	149	-0.0045	[-0.0057, -0.0032]
Asymmetric	10	154	-0.0008	[-0.0020, 0.0004]

Table 1: Agreement between foot-strike event times as recorded at the trunk-mounted IMU versus IMUs mounted at the shanks. *Mean Error* is the mean difference between the foot-strike time as recorded at the shank as a peak in anteroposterior acceleration and the foot-strike time as recorded at the trunk via the method described in section 2.2.

2.2. Movement Analysis

A gait event detection algorithm was developed in the MATLAB computing environment⁴. Video footage and IMU data were synchronised for each capture session, with the video serving as ground-truth reference for the gait events and facilitating the design of the IMU-based detection algorithm.

Event Detection: Unfiltered Y-axis acceleration, a , corresponding to the vertical direction, was identified as being suitable for analysing the periodic motion of each step (see Fig. 1, middle). This signal was first subjected to first order differentiation, yielding *jerk* (Fig. 1, bottom), which at sample n was calculated simply as:

$$j[n] = \frac{a[n] - a[n-1]}{T}. \quad (1)$$

The *stance* phase (foot in contact with ground) was identified as encompassing a region of positive jerk immediately following a local acceleration minimum (below an empirically determined threshold of $a = -1.5$). The toe-off event was found to correspond with the first local maximum during the stance phase.

Vertical acceleration was also used to detect foot-strike events. Foot-strikes were specifically identified as occurring four samples prior to the satisfaction of the following conditions:

- jerk less than -12.5 m s^{-3} ;
- acceleration less than -1.0 m s^{-2} ;
- occurring at least 75 ms after the preceding toe-off.

Upon these conditions being met, a foot-strike was recorded with its sample index and timestamp adjusted accordingly.

Left/Right Limb Identification: The periodic twisting of the upper body while running was visible in the Y-axis data reported by the gyroscopic sensor — *yaw* with respect to its vertical axis — indicating the left-right polarity of the runner’s stride (see Fig. 1, top). Comparison with the video footage showed that polarity could be most reliably identified by taking the sign of the gyroscope Y-axis signal at the toe-off gait event, with positive sign corresponding with the left foot, and negative sign with the right. To improve the reliability of using the gyroscope data in this way a biquadratic low-pass filter was applied to minimize spurious zero-crossings; its low order ensured that minimal delay was introduced.

Cadence: The mean step time, μ_s , at step p , in ms, was first computed from the time intervals between successive toe-off events

⁴MATLAB v9.8.0.1873465 (R2020a)

over the M most recent steps:

$$\mu_s[p] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} (t_o[p-m] - t_o[p-m-1]),$$

where $t_o[p]$ is the absolute timestamp of the p th toe-off. Mean cadence μ_c (steps-per-minute) was then found by dividing the number of milliseconds in one minute by the mean step time:

$$\mu_c[p] = \frac{60000}{\mu_s[p]},$$

Ground Contact Time Balance: First, the average *ground contact time (GCT)* was computed for each foot, e.g. for the right foot at stride q , with an average taken over S strides:

$$\mu_{g,R}[q] = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{m=0}^{S-1} t_{o,R}[q-m] - t_{f,R}[q-m],$$

where $t_{f,R}[q]$ is the time of the q th right foot-strike. Ground contact time balance, A , was computed thus:

$$A[q] = \frac{\mu_{g,R}[q]}{\mu_{g,L}[q] + \mu_{g,R}[q]}.$$

The result is a number $0 \leq A \leq 1$, with a value of 0.5 representing perfect ground-contact symmetry, $A > 0.5$ indicating a bias toward the right foot, and $A < 0.5$ indicating a leftward bias.

2.3. Detection Accuracy

Whereas toe-off event detection was straightforward via identification of a local maximum in the vertical acceleration signal, we had to devise a more complex and targeted analysis approach to detect the foot-strike events from the trunk IMU readings. We validated its accuracy by comparing the detected foot-strike timestamps with shank-recorded tibial acceleration maxima (a proven approach [26]) across capture sessions. As compared with foot-strike events as registered at the shanks (see Table 1), our approach to foot-strike detection described in section 2.2 was accurate on average to within 0.02 s across all capture sessions and exhibited consistent temporal performance (as shown by the 95% confidence intervals). These results are comparable with those described by Lee et al.[25].

3. SONIFICATION SCHEME

3.1. Design Philosophy

Our aim was to design an interactive scheme to provide runners with immediate auditory feedback on temporal asymmetry, both at the individual step level and aggregated over several steps (as previously done for vertical displacement in [8]). We chose to do this by synchronizing synthesized percussive stimuli with gait events (toe-off). Thus, short-term bilateral step time differences were audible as inter-onset interval differences between consecutive stimuli — a task well suited to the auditory system given its excellent temporal resolution [27]. Another reason for doing this was to leverage the known benefits of synchronizing rhythmic stimuli with running gait cadence [23, 24]. Running cadence was hence implicitly conveyed through the tempo of the sonified sequence. To make small momentary cadence changes more salient, we explicitly mapped cadence to the fundamental frequency of the stimuli, such that a faster step rate resulted in higher-pitched sounds (metaphor: higher running frequency \rightarrow higher sound frequency). This design choice is in line with known links between pitch, tempo, and perceived arousal in musical expression [28].

Aggregated GCT asymmetry was conveyed through timbral and spatial changes in the stimuli if a user-defined asymmetry threshold was crossed. Hence, this was designed as a form of *bandwidth* feedback, which would only be provided if performance fell outside a predetermined range (a common approach in past sports-related sonification work [2]). This could help minimize the annoyance and feedback dependence commonly associated with providing continuous feedback [1, 13].

- **Timbral Changes:** As we deemed GCT asymmetry to be an undesirable quality, we chose to represent it using *roughness* and *noise* — sound qualities previously shown to be associated with negative-valence constructs such as error, stress and danger [29]; we realised this through spectral manipulations applied to the sustain and decay portions of the percussive stimuli.
- **Spatial Changes:** As the timbral changes only represented the magnitude of the GCT asymmetry (descriptive feedback [1]), we integrated an intuitive mapping to convey direction, wherein the stimuli were panned to the side with longer measured GCTs (metaphor: skewed gait \rightarrow skewed stereo panorama). This was done to inform runners on how to correct the asymmetry (prescriptive feedback [1]). In addition, asymmetry deviations were made more explicit by the addition of artificial reverberation to indicate *distance* from desirable performance characteristics.

The scheme conveys cadence as well as temporal asymmetry on two timescales through perceptually distinct sound properties, which we believe can allow runners to monitor multiple aspects of gait while avoiding any ambiguity resulting from perceptual interactions [30, 31]. By adjusting the envelope characteristics of the stimuli, it is also possible to perceptually magnify asymmetry at either the individual step level (shorter decay \rightarrow emphasised transients, less pronounced GCT feedback) or aggregated across steps (longer decay \rightarrow deemphasised transients, more pronounced GCT feedback). Our paradigm thereby allows a variety of feedback configurations to be realized by manipulating a single audio signal parameter.

3.2. Implementation

The gait event detection system was ported to C++ for real-time operation, and integrated with a sonification platform developed using the JUCE audio development framework⁵ to yield a stand-alone application. Aside from carrying out gait detection and sonification in real-time, the application provides an interface for loading pre-recorded IMU data plus its associated video footage, re-playing them in real-time, and displaying cadence and GCT balance values (see Fig. 2). It also provides controls for manipulating parameters related to gait detection and sonification on the fly. Our design philosophy was realised via a sonification strategy based on *frequency modulation (FM)* synthesis (chosen for its low computational demands and timbral versatility). Specifically, FM-generated amplitude-enveloped notes are triggered at each toe-off event, whose carrier oscillator frequency is determined by the runner’s cadence. GCT asymmetry feedback is generated by increasing the modulation index as absolute GCT asymmetry increases. In addition, the sound is panned about the stereo field to reflect the degree and direction of gait asymmetry.

A variety of parameters were made modifiable at run-time, to facilitate adjustment of the sonification strategy. Two asymmetry thresholds were implemented: the region below the first threshold represents ‘tolerable’ asymmetry, and in this region a pure sine wave is heard, with no FM applied. Above the first threshold, FM begins to be applied, and above the second threshold artificial reverberation is introduced (8-comb/4-allpass filter based), with the mix between the dry/wet mix of the reverb shifting linearly toward the wet signal with increased asymmetry. Finally, linear amplitude panning is applied in order to reflect the direction of asymmetry. Additional controls were implemented for adjusting aspects of the sonification design during playback. The carrier frequency range and intensity of the frequency modulation effect can be altered, and the decay time of the linear amplitude envelope is modifiable (attack time fixed at 0.05 sec). It is also possible to adjust the number of steps over which average cadence and asymmetry are calculated. A depiction of the mappings making up the sonification strategy can be found in Fig. 3.

FM Synthesis: We built an FM algorithm that generates an increasingly harsh, bell-like timbre as its modulation indices (controlled by GCT balance) are increased. A sine wave carrier oscillator is linearly modulated by three oscillators, M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 , all with fixed non-integer frequency ratios relative to the carrier (1.35, 1.4, and 1.4 respectively — see Fig. 3). M_1 and M_2 act in parallel, M_2 modulated exponentially by M_3 . Additionally, M_2 incorporates the feedback FM technique, routing some of its output back into itself [32]. The output signal, y , is described as follows, for a linearly-modulated FM oscillator:

$$y_{\text{lin}}[n] = A[n] \sin(\omega[n] + m + \alpha y[n - 1]),$$

and for an exponentially-modulated oscillator:

$$y_{\text{exp}}[n] = A[n] \sin(\omega[n] \cdot 2^m + \alpha y[n - 1]),$$

where $A[n]$ is the amplitude envelope value at sample n , $\omega[n]$ the instantaneous phase angle of the oscillator, and α the feedback proportion. The instantaneous amount of modulation, m , is calculated as sum of the output of the oscillator’s M modulators (and

⁵JUCE v6.1.5 <https://juce.com/>

Figure 2: The gait sonification application. Video footage (1) is synchronised with vertical acceleration (2), where gait events and ground contact times are indicated. Recent ground contact times for each foot are listed, plus the mean(3) taken over the number of strides specified by the increment/decrement buttons at the top of the interface (4). Ground contact time balance (5) is displayed at the centre of the interface, with cadence (6) above. Thresholds for ‘tolerable’ and ‘extreme’ asymmetry are adjustable via the slider at the top-right (7). The top-centre slider (8) adjusts the intensity of the modulation effect to be introduced above the ‘tolerable’ threshold. The decay time of notes triggered on toe-off events is adjustable via another slider (9). The slider to the top left (10) adjusts the range of frequencies corresponding to changes in cadence.

recursively for the modulators’ sub-modulators):

$$m = \sum_{k=0}^{M-1} y_k[n].$$

For an oscillator with no modulators, naturally $m = 0$.

The aforementioned parameter for adjusting the intensity of the modulation effect is a scalar applied to A and α ; low values for this parameter result in a bell-like timbre, high values produce a signal comparable to the carrier oscillator being overlaid with white noise.

A repository containing IMU capture data, analysis scripts, and code for the sonification application can be found at <https://github.com/hatchjaw/running-gait-analysis>. A video demonstration of the sonification application in action can be found at <https://youtu.be/xcQAphZupbM>.

3.3. Computational Load

With a view to eventual implementation in an embedded, wearable context, the computational efficiency of the gait event detection algorithm and gait-event sonification strategy was assessed. A

release build of the sonification application with video and other graphical elements disabled, was run on a late-2011 MacBook Pro computer with an eight-core, 2.5 GHz CPU. The UNIX `ps` command-line utility was used to measure the application’s computational load in terms of % CPU usage, revealing mean usage of 7.58% of one core (see Fig. 4).

4. DISCUSSION

The system described in this work represents a proof-of-concept for performing real-time gait event detection and providing intuitive auditory biofeedback on cadence and ground contact time asymmetry during running. Based on the criterion of its consequences for running economy [17], gait asymmetry is a good candidate for sonification, and one that has not been given such treatment elsewhere in the scientific literature. It has also been verified here that gait events can be identified to a good degree of accuracy across a variety of running speeds and styles using data provided by a single inertial sensor, which tallies with findings reported previously [19, 25].

Whether our system can be used to assist a runner in modifying their ground contact time balance to correct temporal asymme-

Figure 3: Block diagram of the mapping scheme and audio synthesis engine. Dark grey blocks indicate aggregated gait features used as sources of control data for the FM parameters. Light grey elements are run-time-modifiable parameters in the interface. Triangular elements indicate constant multiplications, either by the figure within the triangle, or a run-time parameter. Numbers within rounded rectangles indicate constant values. The *modulation amount* parameter is used to scale the modulation indices for oscillators M_1 , M_2 and M_3 , plus the feedback amount for M_2 (leading to more high frequency-rich timbres when FM is applied).

Figure 4: % CPU usage plotted against time for a single run of the gait sonification application. CPU usage samples acquired at 0.1 s intervals. The black horizontal line represents mean % CPU usage (7.58, STD 1.67).

try remains to be investigated. Though a quantifiable gait feature, it has not been established whether asymmetry can be consciously corrected by a runner during the act of running. We are hopeful, however, that our employed embodied metaphors communicating the direction and extent of GCT asymmetry will prove understandable and intuitive to runners. Via an auditory-driven sensorimotor coupling [33], it may be possible for runners to address gait asymmetry in a manner not possible via graphical or textual feedback. We aim to evaluate the informativeness of the sonification design in an upcoming study.

Our system incorporates a novel, flexible sonification scheme, and is a platform that can serve to facilitate a detailed exploration of mapping and sonification design to realise a mapping topology that optimally conveys gait asymmetry in particular. Its flexibility means that it could support a fully fledged evaluation of the salience of the information it provides under a variety of param-

eter mapping conditions; such an investigation could in turn encompass an iterative, participatory sound design process in collaboration with an end-user group [34] — something that would not be possible on the relatively rigid existing running sonification systems to the best of our knowledge. Moreover, the versatility of our FM synthesis framework will allow us to generate a range of timbres and textures, which would be particularly useful in the task of designing user-tailored sound presets to cater to a diversity of individual tastes and preferences [35]. This could take the form of a series of parameters or a list of parameter presets presented to the user via an associated mobile application. There is also further scope for incorporating audio synthesis parameters that are fixed under the present scheme — the frequency ratios used for the modulating oscillators, for example — into the adjustable parameter space. It would also be straightforward to switch to triggering notes at the foot-strike event, rather than the toe-off, to investigate whether users find this to be a more intuitive approach.

Although standing as a proof-of-concept for implementation in real time, the sonification system described here does not operate in a truly interactive fashion, as it presently works by streaming pre-recorded IMU data. However the gait event detection and audio synthesis routines work in real-time and the application can easily be modified to receive data synchronously from an IMU with minimal latency. The Delsys SDK provides a C script (tested in C++) to stream sensor data directly from the sensors⁶. Alternatively low-cost devices such as the M5Stack Core2⁷ can be programmed to transmit inertial data to the JUCE program over WiFi in the form of OSC packets. Indeed, in a laboratory setting, the parameter specifics of the sonification scheme could be rapidly opti-

⁶<https://delsys.com/sdk/>

⁷<https://shop.m5stack.com/products/m5stack-core2-esp32-iot-development-kit>

mised in real time in collaboration with runners, without the need to recompile the sonification application. Following an iterative, user-centred sonification design process of this sort, the system could be implemented in a fully embedded form, on a small, low-cost, low-latency platform such as the *Teensy* microcontroller⁸ to test its real-world corrective potential. The low computational load of the system as a whole (see section 3.3) puts it well within the reach of implementation on such a platform, though care should be taken to minimise the effects of transmission-based latency on audio output.

A limitation of the work presented here is that our gait event detection algorithm was designed and validated based on data from a single healthy male runner who also simulated asymmetric running patterns. It is therefore not known how precisely the algorithm would capture naturally occurring asymmetry patterns in the runner population, particularly mild to moderate asymmetry. Additionally, the foot-strike detection method employed, while accurate enough such that usable ground contact time information can be derived from it, skews early for slower running speeds, and late for faster speeds. Although previous research has shown that data from shank-mounted inertial sensors can serve as ground-truth for foot-strike events [26], ideally the gait event detection system developed here should be refined and verified via comparison with data from optical or pressure sensors like in [19]. There is good reason to believe, however, based on the accuracy of gait event detection from the trunk IMU, that the algorithm will function robustly for a variety of runners. In future work, we will evaluate the accuracy of the gait event detection algorithm during overground as well as treadmill running with multiple runners exhibiting a range of temporal asymmetry patterns.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The sonification platform we built can serve as a versatile framework to facilitate the evaluation of our devised sonification scheme. The parametric flexibility and scope for real-time adjustment can support a rapid, iterative process of user-centred sonification design. The sonification scheme presents multiple streams of kinematic feedback to the runner in an intuitive way with the aim of drawing their attention to changes in cadence and ground contact asymmetry without distracting them from the act of running. Although the informative and corrective potential of the scheme is yet to undergo rigorous evaluation, we believe that the potential of sonifying temporal asymmetry during running is worthy of investigation, and that the present work is an important first step in this direction.

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Author Contributions: TAR was responsible for devising the project proposal, system design, and technical implementation as part of his MSc. studies at Aalborg University, Copenhagen. PRK assisted with data collection, analysis, interaction design philosophy, and writing. Both authors approved of the final manuscript.

⁸<https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/>

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